

MASIVULE I-ANTIEKE STUDIES

From trauma to change

A transformative research- and discussion-group of students, staff, and alumni from the Department of Ancient Studies

Background and aims

Authorities often assume that everyone is equally welcome and similarly accommodated at tertiary educational institutions. While this should be the case and, we believe, does indeed guide the policies of universities in South Africa, our own experience speaks to the contrary. Whether as undergraduate and postgraduate students, doctoral candidates, postdoctoral fellows, or staff members, we have – to a distinct extent – felt marginalized or excluded in our immediate university context, the Department of Ancient Studies. We have been unable to recognize ourselves in the culture of this department and its structures, and we have suffered diverse types of institutional and epistemic violence generated by this space. Interactions with the Department of Ancient Studies which we have experienced as **white-centered, patriarchal, hierarchical, and heteronormative**, have marked us both as scholars and human beings.

The MASIVULE i-ANTIEKE STUDIES project – or MAS – aims to provide a safe platform for all those who have been marginalized, othered, and/or traumatized during their studies and work at the Department of Ancient Studies. It will allow all such subjects to jointly reflect on their past and present in the environment that they have perceived as oppressive; to recognize commonalities in, what appears as, disconnected life events and, after analyzing them with an academic rigor and systematicity of **decolonial, feminist/intersectional, anarchist, and queer theories**, to share these experiences with others through scholarly articles; and ultimately to formulate a proposal to improve the conditions of those who learn and work within this space.

The MAS platform will be both physical and virtual. Our meetings will be conducted in person and online and will be open to anyone who wishes to participate. We plan to invite decolonial, feminist, anarchist, and queer scholars from around the world and establish relationships with similar collectives, especially those that have been labeled as disruptive by the authority and agents of the status-quo. We wish to foster generative debates in which all voices will be heard, all perspectives will be valued, and all opinions will be respected. The two principles guiding our meetings will be respect and transparency.

However, the MAS project will not only generate reflections, discussions, scholarly articles, and policy proposals. Even more importantly, it will serve as a collective support for each individual in their struggles. We hope that it will allow us to overcome our past and current trauma emerging from and related to the systemic issues inbuilt in the structures and institutions of the Department of Ancient Studies

Framework

Our research will be carried out within four – compatible and complementary yet autonomous and distinct – paradigms: decoloniality/decolonization, feminism/intersectionality, anarchism, and queer theory. While all of them apply to our research, not all of them are equally embraced by all the members of our collective.

Decolonization is an empirical process rooted in decoloniality – it constitutes an action or activity that is “confined to specific [temporal and] empirical dimensions” (Maldonado-Torres 2016, 10; 2017, 120). In contrast, **decoloniality** refers to a type of a (broadly understood philosophical) attitude or orientation that is “created by the [...] process [...] of [...] decolonization” and involves metaphysics, ontology, and epistemics, as well as multiple matrices of power relationships and theories of praxes (Maldonado-Torres 2016, 10; Kessi, Marks, and Ramugondo 2020). Decolonization and decoloniality coexist in an entanglement: decolonization performs and applies decoloniality, while decoloniality guides decolonization and results from it.

As their names indicate it, decolonization and decoloniality are inherently relational concepts. The privative prefix *de-* explicitly signals that decolonization and decoloniality counter, reverse, and ultimately eliminate two other phenomena, namely colonization (typically referred to as colonialism) and coloniality (Maldonado Torres 2016; 2017). Colonialism is a process “locked in the past” that, like decolonization, concerns specific spatial-temporal coordinates (Maldonado-Torres 2016, 10). In contrast, coloniality refers to “the [...] colonial matrix of power, being, and knowledge that became a central, if not a constitutive, dimension of [white] Western modernity and its hegemonic civilization project” (Maldonado-Torres 2017, 111; see also Grosfoguel 2011). In addition to colonialism and coloniality, scholars distinguish ‘epicoloniality’. Epi-coloniality refers to “the features of coloniality that pervade and supersede systems and relations of power” as well as “phenomena for which the cause may or may not be directly traced to legacies or histories of overt or observed colonial encounters, but in which power relations and outcomes are recognizably colonial” (Kessi, Marks, and Ramugondo 2020, 271).

Decolonization and decoloniality are governed by two, certainly interrelated, teleological principles and produce two types of effects. On the one hand, decolonization and decoloniality negate and undo unjust presuppositions, dehumanizing practices, and brutal institutions inherited from or imposed by the (epi)colonial forces, as well as the various power configurations that typify (epi)colonial reality (Grosfoguel 2011; Maldonado-Torres 2016, 10; 2017, 120; Kessi, Marks, and Ramugondo 2020, 271). On the other hand, by drawing on forces that are local and transcend (epi)colonial legacy and its “Capitalist/Patriarchal Western-centric/Christian-centric Modern/Colonial World-System” (Grosfoguel 2013, 89), decoloniality and decolonization imagine and create alternative presuppositions, practices, and institutions (Kessi, Marks, and Ramugondo 2020, 271). They formulate and execute “counter-discourses” and “counter-knowledges”, and a variety of acts that “open up multiple other forms of being in the world” (Maldonado-Torres 2016, 10). Decolonization and decoloniality may pertain to and be exercised in four, closely interconnected and intertwined domains: personal, relational, structural, and epistemic (Kessi, Marks, and Ramugondo 2020).

Intersectionality theory is an expression of both **feminism** and **critical race theory**. As a framework, it stresses not just the marginalization of women, but the interactions between interlocking social structures that oppress in ways that are similar and different depending on the positionality of the individual (Lutz, Herrera Vivar, and Supik 2011:2). Within this framework, the category of “woman” is deconstructed to emphasize the differences between women and to take into consideration the convergence of various oppressions within one lived experience. Intersectionality provides a lens through which analysis of the mutual co-constitution of categories of social differentiation can become productive; not only does it point to the layers of injustice affecting the lives of the multiply marginalized in specific ways, it also implies a deconstruction of those social categories and the structures that produce them so that something new can be thought in its stead. There is therefore a double focus in intersectionality on the specificity of individual experiences of marginalization and oppression on the one hand and the larger structures and institutions that support the former on the other hand. The latter reaches far beyond structures of soft power such as social attitudes to also encompass formal structures such as education, law, governance, and institutional culture. Because of this, intersectionality allows for an approach which takes into account not only gendered feminist movements, but also racial, political, economic, and social discussions. Indeed, the term was first coined by feminist legal scholar Kimberlé Crenshaw, whose analysis of the different experiences of black women and white women in courts of law showed that despite promises of equality before the law, the reality is not quite so (Crenshaw 1989:1991). Pointing to “women” as a marginalized group tends to center white women’s experiences at the expense of black women, who face both sexism and racism within the same structures.

In the thirty years since Crenshaw first published the article that coined the term, intersectionality has generated sustained debate, in part because of its focus on the experiences of black women. While some criticize the theory for over-emphasizing race, it is by no means limited to the intersection of race and sex. It offers a multifaceted approach that can explain how race, sex, gender, class, disability, sexuality, ethnicity, language, and any number of further social categories intersect and, in many ways, determine what kind of life a person can live. In a 2020 interview with *Time Magazine*, Crenshaw defines intersectionality as a “prism, for seeing the way in which various forms of inequality often operate together and exacerbate each other” (Steinmetz 2020). The list of inequalities is thus non-exhaustive; there are always further structures of power to be examined, analyzed, and critiqued (Carbado et al. 2013:304). Intersectionality theory further stresses privilege as much as it does oppression – if one has to acknowledge that they have faced structural oppression along the axes of class, gender, etc., they must also acknowledge that those same structures have privileged them along other axes, such as race and able-bodiedness. As a result, intersectionality offers a framework to understand the immensely complex variations in human experience, to deconstruct the mechanisms that privilege some over others, and to imagine a different, more just world in the absence of these structures.

Anarchism is “skepticism” about (McLaughlin 2021:23), “critique” of (Carson 2021:365), and/or “opposition” to (Clark 2007:6) structural and agential domination recognizable in all hierarchies and authorities (McLaughlin 2021). Contrary to such domination-driven systems, where order is achieved by externally imposed policies, punitive laws, and coercion (Bowen and Purkis 2004), in an anarchist system, harmony and justice result from freely constituted relationships that couple individuals and groups (Kropotkin 1995). In this system, the individual and the communal are not opposed but rather reinforce one another – the individual becomes freer, and the community becomes more united (Clark 2007).

Similar to decoloniality/decolonization and intersectionality, anarchism exploits two main methods to achieve its goals: a destructive one and a creative one (Ferrell 2009). The destructive method involves revolution – a demolition of hierarchical structures (Bakunin 1974; Ferrell 2009; Byas and Christmas 2021) because they cause, preserve, and reinforce domination and thus oppression (Deleon and Love 2009). This oppression is in fact inevitable: by allowing for only a unidirectional communication channel (i.e., from top down), hierarchical structures are systematically stupid and opaque. They locate authority holders in imaginary worlds, in which these agents gradually experience a “psychotic break with reality”. This epistemic dissonance leads, in turn, to the paranoiac mistrust of the authority holders towards lower echelons and ultimately produces obsessive surveillance, castigatory policies, and paralyzing bureaucracy (Carson 2021:367). The creative facet of anarchism replaces hierarchical structures with horizontal ones. Horizontal structures are self-organized and self-managed; they allow for a bidirectional information flow and thus accumulate the intelligence of their parts; they are propelled by common, yet not necessarily identical, interests and appear as legible to all members; they are fluid – because they are self-reflected and self-critiquing – and adapt fast to a changing environment (Armeline 2009; Deleon and Love 2009; Ferrell 2009; Carson 2021).

In pedagogy, anarchism recognizes that universities are manipulation tools exploited by the authority to preserve and reinforce itself (Freire 2000). Universities are designed to produce obedient, complacent, and docile bodies that will adhere to established values, including capitalism and official religions (Chomsky 2003; Deleon and Love 2009; Kaltefleiter and Nocella 2012). Universities replicate a hierarchical feudal system with teachers assuming the role of oppressors (Graeber 2009), with coercive policies imposed from the top, and with an army of bureaucratic obsessions: numerical grades, standardized curricula, and uniformized tests (Chomsky 2003; Armeline 2009). Nevertheless, universities can, at the same time, be a birthplace of resistance that centers self-government, reason instead of doctrine, non-formality, equality of participation, and freedom of choice (Gribble 2004; Deleon and Love 2009). This can be achieved by being subversive and creating alternatives, such as: approaching truth humbly as constructed and participative; contextualizing histories and ideologies; designing learning and teaching as cooperative; involving students in knowledge production; replacing teacher-student coercive lecturing with persuasion, facilitation, and encouragement; constructing horizontal structures inside and outside of the classroom; viewing everyone as potentially curious and creative; allowing students to pursue their curiosities and interests; and creating alternative forms of evaluation (Gribble 2004; Armeline 2009; Kaltefleiter and Nocella 2012; Noterman and Pusey 2012; Currie-Knight 2021).

Queer theory posits that the expectation of the (hetero)normative is damaging to both queer and straight individuals. Teresa de Lauretis (1991) first uses the term queer theory in order to reconceptualize male and female homosexuality as social experiences in their own right, not defined in opposition to the heterosexual norm. Within this reconceptualization, de Lauretis (1991) unpacks lesbian and gay experiences as separate from one another, identifies the ways in which race and racial expectation creates biases in sex and sexuality, and criticizes the notion that heterosexuality be a sexual norm or benchmark at all. These ideas build on those presented and developed by writers such as Foucault (1976) and Rubin (1984) who begin to reject biological explanations for sex and begin to reconsider the notion of a sexual binary. Judith Butler (1990) also draws on these ideas to understand the performativity of gender, suggesting that gender and sexuality are not inherently biological truths, but are rather learned and performed realities. Thus, queer theory becomes an intersectional approach to understanding gender and sex through its rejection of heteronormative ideas and a deconstruction of the institutions which perpetuate the binaries thereof.

Queer theory reassures us that binarisms are untenable; that the hegemonic establishment must constantly be questioned; that hetero-normative institutions should be challenged. To 'queer' is to be politically agentic and active instead of remaining silent. Queer is constantly in the pursuit to (re)create one's own identity through conscious actions instead of passively receiving it. Queer entails embracing, unapologetically, one's own queerness instead of hiding it for the comfort of the heteronormative majority (Kirsch 2001; Huffer 2010; 2013; Wilcox 2017).

Overall, we embrace **methodological promiscuity** (Wilcox 2017; Huffer 2010). This type of methodological approach should not be viewed as cherry-picking theories that suit one's argument. It is rather an unavoidable consequence of understanding any real-world system as a complex system, which is a widely accepted view in current scholarship. That is, any single model of a real-world complex system is incomplete and fragmentary due to the non-additivity of such systems and their inherent emergence (Auyang 1998; Hooker 2011a, 2011b; Cilliers et al. 2013). There is no unique model of a complex system because no perspective can represent all its properties. Instead, the study of a complex system necessitates a number of perspectives with the exploration of perspectives constituting the fundamental epistemological principle in the analysis (Cilliers et al. 2013). Distinct perspectives are aimed at dealing with the behavior of distinct modules – some being, for instance, appropriate for the study of atomic levels, while others being used in the study of global levels. Similarly, different levels and aspects of our being in the world need to be studied with different methodologies, each designed specifically to a particular level or aspect. Echoing Wilcox's (2017 [online]) view on queer studies, "[we] believe that the methodological and theoretical promiscuities that [...] characterize [our approach] are a sign of [the ...] strength" of our analysis – not its weakness.

Research plan

We envision that our project will involve three main phases during which we will consecutively share our experiences, analyze them critically, and propose solutions:

Outcome

The ultimate outcome of the project will be articles that we will submit to accredited journals in the area of tertiary education, decolonial, feminist, and queer studies, as well as multilingualism.

However, apart from publications, we hope that our project will result in the identification of changes that should be implemented in the Department of Ancient Studies to render this space more inclusive and less violent. By doing so, we believe our work will be beneficial for the university community and management.

Team

Lunette Warren (Independent – Department of Ancient Studies' alumna) is an historian and educator. They have a PhD in Ancient Cultures from Stellenbosch University and a Postgraduate Certificate in Education from the same institution. They are a first-generation university graduate from a working-class background, a lifelong learner and a firm believer in possibility. Their research has increasingly focused on the role of education in legitimizing structures of social differentiation, the concurrent formation of the self along these lines, and the ontological negation of non-normative ways of being within this framework. This research has been funded by the National Research Foundation's Innovation doctoral and postdoctoral fellowships, the Andrew Mellon Foundation and the DAAD. Lunette's work is interdisciplinary, stretching across the boundaries of ancient studies, gender studies, education, and philosophy.

Jessica Van den Brink has recently completed her MA in Ancient Cultures through the Department of Ancient Studies at Stellenbosch University. Her preoccupation with the Ancient World stems from the fact that the Ancient World inherently lends itself to various lenses and approaches which can help to understand and unravel modern experiences of gender, sexuality, race, and globalization, among many others. Having grown up a third-culture kid, and being the first in her family to pursue higher education, she is the product of both global experiences and local narratives. The intersectionality of this experience, filled with alienation, adventure, and adaptation, has given her a willingness to learn and unlearn and hopefully encourage similar open-mindedness in those around her.

Cliff Sekowe is currently pursuing his MA studies in ancient languages through the Department of Ancient Studies at Stellenbosch University. Cliff is a trained theologian with a passion for teaching. He was born in the radically multicultural township of SOWETO and for a long part of his life resided in the equally culturally diverse SOSHANGUVE – a place whose name is an acronym for Sotho, Shangaan, Nguni, and Venda. As a result, he fluently speaks all the African languages of South Africa. He is a passionate advocate for social justice. He is the founder of Pholoso Ministries. He hosts a podcast channel where he interviews scholars and explores how scripture can shake our ethical imagination and disrupt the violent and unjust system in which we live. He believes that he can combat the interpretation of the Bible as a tool enabling the preservation of the status quo.

Luiz Ribeiro has a PhD in Religion (University of Toronto). He held a post-doctoral fellowship at the Department of Ancient Studies. He is a historian of Greco-Roman Antiquity and Sexuality, stubbornly Foucaultian, Rive Gauche existentialist, and Beatnik poet in previous lives.

Michael Kwadwo Okyere Asante is a Lecturer in the Department of General Studies at the University of Environment and Sustainable Development, Somanya, Ghana and a first generation PhD student in ancient cultures in the Department of Ancient Studies, Stellenbosch University, where he is working on a re-reading of the position of the individual in Plato's 'Republic' through the lens of Afro-communitarianism. Michael has been involved in various initiatives addressing the need for decolonisation in the curriculum, teaching and research that occurs in the field of Classics. He currently co-edits the special issue of the Bulletin of the Institute of Classical Studies (BICS) on 'Decolonising Classics in Africa: Strategies, Challenges and Prospects' (forthcoming June 2022) and sits on the board of the Graduate Student Committee of the Society for Classical Studies, the first person from the African continent to serve in such capacity.

Alexander Andrason (senior lecturer in the Department of Ancient Studies – Stellenbosch University) holds three PhD degrees: in Semitic Languages (University Complutense in Madrid, Spain), in African Languages (Stellenbosch University, South Africa), and in General Linguistics (University of Iceland). He is a global nomad who was brought up in a multicultural environment and, since adolescence, has resided, studied, and worked in eight European and African countries; a hyper-multilingual whose language repertoire draws on forty languages, ten of which he speaks with native or native-like proficiency; a teacher who refuses to stop being a student but welcomes the wisdom of others by pursuing studies at various new universities; a pluri-disciplinary scholar who, being fascinated by life and reality in all their aspects and diversity, thrives at disciplines and theories' crossroads; an idealist who fights for the preservation and revitalization of ethnic, cultural, and language minorities; and, perhaps most importantly, being an eternal immigrant himself, a fervent defender of the immigrants' cause.

References

- Armaline, W. 2009. Thoughts on anarchist pedagogy and epistemology. In *Contemporary Anarchist Studies*, edited by R. Amster, A. DeLeon, L.A. Fernandez, A.J. Nocella, and D. Shannon, 136-146. London: Routledge.
- Auyang S. 1998. *Foundations of Complex-System Theories*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Bakunin, M. 1974. *Michael Bakunin: Selected Writings*. A. Lehning, ed. New York: Grove.
- Bowen, J. and J. Purkis. 2004. Introduction: Why anarchism still matters. In *Changing Anarchism. Anarchist Theory and Practice in a Global Age*, edited by J. Purkis and J. Bowen, 1-19. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Butler, J. 1990. *Gender Trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity*. New York: Routledge.
- Byas, J.L. and B. Christmas. 2021. Methodological Anarchism. In *The Routledge Handbook of Anarchy and Anarchist Thought*, edited by G. Chartier and C. Van Schoelandt, 53-75. New York: Routledge.
- Carbado, D.W., K.W. Crenshaw, V.M. Mays, and B. Tomlinson. 2013. Intersectionality: Mapping the movements of a theory. *Du Bois Review* 10(2): 303-312.
- Carson, K. 2021. An anarchist critique of power relations within institutions. In *The Routledge Handbook of Anarchy and Anarchist Thought*, edited by G. Chartier and C. Van Schoelandt, 365-380. New York: Routledge.
- Chomsky, N. 2003. The function of schools: Subtler and cruder methods of control. In *Education as Enforcement: The Militarization and Corporatization of Schools*, edited by K.J. Saltman and D.A. Gabbard, 25-35. New York: Routledge.
- Cilliers, P., H.C. Biggs, S. Blignaut, A.G. Choles, J.S. Hofmeyr, G.P. W. Jewitt, and D. J. Roux. 2013. Complexity, modeling, and natural resource management. *Ecology and Society* 18(3): 1–12.
- Clark, S. 2007. *Living Without Domination. The Possibility of an Anarchist Utopia*. Aldershot: Ashgate.
- Crenshaw, K. 1989. Demarginalizing the intersection of race and sex: A black feminist critique of antidiscrimination doctrine, feminist theory and antiracist politics. *University of Chicago Legal Forum* 139-167.
- Crenshaw, K. 1991. Mapping the margins: Intersectionality, identity politics, and violence against women of color. *Stanford Law Review* 43(6): 1241-1299.
- Currie-Knight, K. 2021. Anarchist approaches to education. In *The Routledge Handbook of Anarchy and Anarchist Thought*, edited by G. Chartier and C. Van Schoelandt, 360-364 New York: Routledge.
- De Lauretis, T. 1991. Queer theory. Lesbian and gay sexualities: An introduction. *Queer Theory: Lesbian and Gay Sexualities* 3(2): iii-xviii.
- DeLeon, A. and K. Love. 2009. Anarchist theory as radical critique: challenging hierarchies and domination in the social and “hard” sciences. In *Contemporary Anarchist Studies*, edited by R. Amster, A. DeLeon, L.A. Fernandez, A.J. Nocella, and D. Shannon, 159-165. London: Routledge.
- Ferrell, J. 2009. Against method, against authority . . . for anarchy. In *Contemporary Anarchist Studies*, edited by R. Amster, A. DeLeon, L.A. Fernandez, A.J. Nocella, and D. Shannon, 73-81. London: Routledge.
- Foucault, M. 1976. *The History of Sexuality*. New York: Pantheon Books.

- Gribble, D. 2004. Good news for Francisco Ferrer – How anarchist ideals in education have survived around the world. In *Changing Anarchism. Anarchist Theory and Practice in a Global Age*, edited by J. Purkis and J. Bowen, 163-180. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Grosfoguel, R. 2011. Decolonizing post-colonial studies and paradigms of political-economy: Transmodernity, decolonial thinking, and global coloniality." *TRANSMODERNITY: Journal of Peripheral Cultural Production of the Luso-Hispanic World* 1(1): 1–38.
- Grosfoguel, R. 2013. The structure of knowledge in westernized universities. Epistemic racism/sexism and the four genocides/epistemicides of the long 16th century. *Human Architecture: Journal of the Sociology of Self-Knowledge* 11(1): 73–90.
- Hooker C. 2011a. Introduction to philosophy of complex systems: A. In *Philosophy of Complex Systems*, edited by C. Hooker, 3–90. Benjamins: Amsterdam.
- Hooker C. 2011b. Introduction to philosophy of complex systems: B. In *Philosophy of Complex Systems*, edited by C. Hooker, 841–910. Benjamins: Amsterdam.
- Huffer, L. 2010. *Mad for Foucault*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Huffer, L. 2013. *Are the Lips a Grave? A Queer Feminist on the Ethics of Sex*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Kaltefleiter, C. and A. Nocella. 2012. Anarchy in the academy: Staying true to anarchism as an academic-activist. In *Anarchist Pedagogies: Collective Actions, Theories, and Critical Reflections on Education*, edited by R.H. Haworth, 175-199. Oakland: PM Press.
- Kessi, S., Z. Marks, and E. Ramugondo. 2020. Decolonizing African Studies. *Critical African Studies* 12(3): 271–282.
- Kirsch, M.H. 2001. *Queer Theory and Social Change*. New York: Routledge.
- Kropotkin, P. 1995. *Kropotkin: The Conquest of Bread and Other Writings*. Edited by M. Shatz. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Lutz, H.M., M.T. Herrera Vivar, and L. Supik. 2011 Framing Intersectionality: An Introduction. In *Framing Intersectionality: Debates on a Multi-Faceted Concept in Gender Studies*, edited by Lutz, H.M., M.T. Herrera Vivar, and L. Supik, 1-25. Aldershot: Ashgate.
- Maldonado-Torres, N. 2016. Outline of ten theses on coloniality and decoloniality. Frantz Fanon Foundation. <https://fondation-frantzfanon.com/outline-of-ten-theses-on-coloniality-and-decoloniality/>
- Maldonado-Torres, N. 2017. Decolonial turn. In *Twenty-Five Years of Turns in Latin American Studies, Culture, Power and Politics*, edited by J. Poblete, 111–127. New York: Routledge.
- McLaughlin, P. 2021. Anarchism, anarchists, and anarchy. In *The Routledge Handbook of Anarchy and Anarchist Thought*, edited by G. Chartier and C. Van Schoelandt, 15-27. New York: Routledge.
- Noterman, E. and A. Pusey. 2012. Inside, outside, and on the edge of the academy: Experiments in radical pedagogies. In *Anarchist Pedagogies: Collective Actions, Theories, and Critical Reflections on Education*, edited by R.H. Haworth, 200-216. Oakland: PM Press.

Rubin, G. 1984. Thinking sex: Notes for a radical theory of the politics of sexuality. In *Pleasure and Danger: Exploring Female Sexuality*, edited by C.S. Vance, 267-319. London: Pandora.

Steinmetz, K. 2020. She coined the term 'Intersectionality' over 30 years ago. Here's what it means to her today. [online] *Time*. Available at: <<https://time.com/5786710/kimberle-crenshaw-intersectionality/>> [Accessed 10 February 2022].

Wilcox, M. 2017. Methodological promiscuity and undisciplined intellectual orgies. *The Scholar & Feminist Online* 14.2. Available online: <http://sfoonline.barnard.edu/queer-religion>.